

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF STOKIN STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH TOXOPLASMOSIS

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Abstract

The problem of opportunistic infections is becoming an urgent problem of modern times is becoming, which is a constant increase in the number of people infected with HIV, it is related to the increase in aggressive treatment methods of oncopathologies. This infections Pathogens that can normally cause disease in healthy individuals caused by Up to 20 typical causative agents of opportunistic infections are known, and in modern infectious diseases this list is constantly growing. without symptoms: 60% - cytomegalovirus, 90% - first and second type herpavirus, 30% are toxoplasma carriers.

During the research, 100 people infected with toxoplasmosis were studied. The research shows that during the exacerbation of the disease, the level of cytokines increases in comparison to healthy people, year-6, year-10. Cytokine balance depends on the severity of the disease. The aim of the study is to study the level of production of the main cytokines (year-6, year-10) that help to study the functional activity of immunocompetent cells and the severity of the infectious process in patients infected with toxoplasma.

Keywords: Cytokines, interleukin-1, interleukin-6, interleukin-10, toxoplasmosis

At present, the high level of infection of the population with toxoplasmosis, the damage of the fetus inside the womb, the loss of the organ of vision and its functions - even leading to blindness, and the fact that it causes severe relapses in AIDS patients create serious problems for the health system.

Immunity during toxoplasmosis is non-sterile. The effectiveness of the defense system depends on the factors of humoral and cellular immunity. Against the background of the normal state of cellular immunity, the synthesis of specific antibodies prevents the symptomless passing of the disease, re-infection, and transplant transmission of the pathogen.

Despite the adaptive capabilities of the immune system, changes in its components become chronic and lead to the formation of immunopathologies. As modulators of the immune system, cytokines ensure intercellular cooperation, positive and negative immune regulation. Cytokines play an important role in regulating the immune response by ensuring the proliferation and differentiation of immunocompetent immune cells. (4,5,6) At the same time, immune system dysfunctions against the background of immunodeficiency cause dysfunction in the cytokine system. It has been proven that cytokines affect the endothelial cells infected with viruses and cause the inflammation process to decrease.

Cytokines simulate the antiviral effects of polymorphonuclear leukocytes of macrophages, natural killer and other cells. (7,8) The character of cytokines depends on their levels.

The diagnostic importance of determining the level of cytokines is related to their role in the pathogenesis of infection. The products synthesized by Th-1 (11-2, il-3, il-13, etc.) (year-4, year 5, year-6, year-10, year-13) are responsible for the activity of antibodies. The importance of the evaluation of the cytokine content is to determine the relationship between the level of cytokines in a certain patient and the course of the disease (8).

The purpose of the study: The purpose of the study is to study the production level of the main cytokines (year-1, year-6, year-10) that help to study the functional activity of immunocompetent cells and the severity of the infectious process in patients infected with toxoplasma.

Materials and methods: In the studies, the immune indicators of 100 patients infected with toxoplasma (55 women, 45 men) were studied. Of these, 50 patients had mild, 35 moderate, and 15 severe cases. 30 completely healthy people were selected as the control group. The diagnosis was made on the basis of clinical manifestations and determination of specific antibodies against toxoplasmosis by immunoenzyme analysis.

Patients were studied in the acute and remission stages of the disease, and during the exacerbation period, patients received standard antiviral therapy. In order to evaluate the cytokine profile in patients infected with toxoplasma, the concentration of cytokines of year-1, year-6, year-year-10 was determined by the IFA method.

The results of the conducted research were processed with Microsoft Excel and statistics computer programs. At this time, regression and correlation methods were used.

Conclusion and discussion

In patients with relapsed toxoplasmosis, during the exacerbation of the disease - the first 3 days, the level of il-1 rose to the maximum level. During the remission period, this indicator decreased, but did not reach the indicator of healthy (considered) individuals.

The concentration of il-1 in the blood serum depended on the severity of the disease. Taking into account the role of il-1 in the elimination of the pathogen, this change can be considered legitimate. .

As a result of the immunostimulatory effect of Il-1, differentiation and functional activity of lymphocytes, synthesis of Il-2 antibodies by lymphocytes, proliferation of lymphocytes increases. Thus, il-1 has a wide spectrum of biological activity; By increasing the functional activity of the T-set of cellular immunity and the cells of the natural spleen, it induces the synthesis of its own interferon in the host organism (endogenous). In patients with toxoplasmosis, an increase in the level of il-6 during the period of exacerbation of the disease was observed, while during the period of remission, this level was lower than the norm. (table 1)

The change in the amount of il-6 in the blood samples of a patient with toxoplasmosis also depends on the severity of the disease. IL-6, a typical inflammatory cytokine, activates neutrophils and increases their functional activity.

Il-6 activates the synthesis of immunoglobulins belonging to IgM, IgG, IgA class and acute phase proteins in hepatocytes. It stimulates the proliferation and differentiation of acute phase proteins and T lymphocytes. On the other hand, it determines the production of 1-6 1-1

Table 1

The composition of the main stocks in patients with toxoplasmosis according to the period of the study.

Studied Indicators	Research period	N	Xmin- Xmax	X± m	P
IL-I	Healthy	30	32-64	48±1.9	-
	I	100	90-194	120±9.2	<0.001
	II	35	85-164	100±5.2	<0.001
	III	65	72-118	82±2.1	<0.001
IL-6	Healthy	30	28-36	25±1.6	-
	I	100	65-88	52±1.2	<0.001
	II	35	52-70	46±2.5	<0.001
	III	65	38-64	39±1.4	<0.001
IL-10	Healthy	30	40-63	40.2±0.7	-
	I	100	57-84	78.3±0.98	<0.001
	II	35	46-76	65.9±0.94	<0.001
	III	65	40-58	37.3±0.62	<0.001

Note; I-acute period of the disease II-early convalescence period, III-delayed convalescence period, P-N-amount of studies X-average numerical value,+M - average numerical error. Il-10 acts as a negative regulator for inflammatory processes. This cytokine is associated with a decrease in cytokine production and antigen presentation in Th-1 cells and monocytes. Il-10 is a regulatory and anti-inflammatory alternative for macrophages, but also Th-2 and Th-1 therefore, il-10 is an anti-inflammatory cytokine for all Th-1 cells and prevents inflammation. It is assumed that the immunosuppressiveness of viruses is controlled by affecting the balance of il-10 and il-12. the reduction of markers (il-1B-6-il-10), at the same time stimulates proliferation of B lymphocytes and humoral immunity.

Activated T lymphocytes increase il-10, and its level increases during the exacerbation of the disease, but decreases during remission, but is higher than the norm. When the course of the disease increases, the level of il-10 stocks also increases. il-1B, il-6 and il-10 stocks level increased compared to healthy people.

Thus, the study of the role of cytokines in a given infection will allow us to understand a number of mech-

anisms by which internal cellular processes and inter-cellular interactions are used to maintain the body's defense forces and the life cycle of replication. helps to develop a control system for toxoplasmosis infection.

Results

1. The study of the production of cytokines in patients showed that, compared to healthy donors, an increase in the synthesis of il-1B, il-6, and il-10 cytokines is noticeable during the exacerbation of diseases. In parallel, the level of cytokines gradually decreases in the positive dynamics of the disease.

2. The balance of stocks depends on the severity of the disease; as the disease worsens, the level of stocks also rises.

3. The study of Stoke's balance allows to understand the pathogenesis of the infection, the tropism and virulence of the virus, thereby helping to develop a control system for toxoplasmosis infection.

References

1. López-Yglesias AH, Camanzo E, Martin AT, Araujo AM, Yarovinsky F. TLR11-independent inflammasome activation is critical for CD4+ T cell-derived IFN-γ production and host resistance to *Toxoplasma gondii*. *PLoS Pathog.* 2019 Jun

13;15(6):e1007872. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1007872. PMID: 31194844; PMCID: PMC6599108.

2. Schmitt N, Ueno H. Regulation of human helper T cell subset differentiation by cytokines. *Curr Opin Immunol.* 2015 Jun;34:130-6. doi: 10.1016/j.coi.2015.03.007. Epub 2015 Apr 11. PMID: 25879814; PMCID: PMC4465198.

3. Butcher BA, Kim L, Panopoulos AD, Watowich SS, Murray PJ, Denkers EY. IL-10-independent STAT3 activation by *Toxoplasma gondii* mediates suppression of IL-12 and TNF-alpha in host macrophages. *J Immunol.* 2005 Mar 15;174(6):3148-52. doi: 10.4049/jimmunol.174.6.3148. PMID: 15749841.

4. Alicia Benson, Sean Murray, Prashanthi Divakar, Nikolay Burnaevskiy, Reed Pifer, James Forman, Felix Yarovinsky; Microbial Infection-Induced Expansion of Effector T Cells Overcomes the Suppressive Effects of Regulatory T Cells via an IL-2 Deprivation Mechanism. *J Immunol* 15 January 2012; 188 (2): 800–810.

5. Salinas N, Olguín JE, Castellanos C, Saavedra R. T cell suppression in vitro during *Toxoplasma gondii* infection is the result of IL-2 competition between Tregs and T cells leading to death of proliferating T cells. *Scand J Immunol.* 2014 Jan;79(1):1-11. doi: 10.1111/sji.12120. PMID: 24117537.

6. Boyman O, Sprent J. The role of interleukin-2 during homeostasis and activation of the immune system. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2012 Feb 17;12(3):180-90. doi: 10.1038/nri3156. PMID: 22343569.

7. Bachmann MF, Wolint P, Walton S, Schwarz K, Oxenius A. Differential role of IL-2R signaling for CD8+ T cell responses in acute and chronic viral infections. *Eur J Immunol.* 2007 Jun;37(6):1502-12. doi: 10.1002/eji.200637023. PMID: 17492805.

8. Pipkin ME, Sacks JA, Cruz-Guilloty F, Lichtenheld MG, Bevan MJ, Rao A. Interleukin-2 and inflammation induce distinct transcriptional programs that promote the differentiation of effector cytolytic T cells. *Immunity.* 2010 Jan 29;32(1):79-90. doi: 10.1016/j.immuni.2009.11.012. Epub 2010 Jan 21. PMID: 20096607; PMCID: PMC2906224.